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SMART ICU for patient monitoring using IoT

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Introduction: In this era, wireless communication plays a significant role in clinical fields in monitoring the patient condition. The development of Internet of Things brings out new inventions to the world in which devices can make decision of their own, can organize their work and it can coordinate with other devices. Clinical fields are in the need of continues health monitoring system to monitor patient’s health from anywhere. The proposed Smart Patient Monitoring System helps to track patient’s health condition continuously with the help of ThinkSpeak and IFTTT.

Methods: The system includes LM35 Temperature Sensor, Pulse Rate Sensor, Panic Push button, Arduino UNO Board, ESP8266 Wi-Fi Module, ThingSpeak Cloud Platform (Figure 1). The system will monitor the temperature, pressure of the patient in real- time. During an emergency, the patient can press the Panic Push button connected to Arduino Uno which in turn connected with ESP8266 Wi-Fi module sends an alert through Mail or SMS to the patient’s relatives and the doctor in charge.

Figure 1: Block diagram of the system

Results & Discussions: When the temperature and pulse rate crosses the normal fixed levels the values are recorded in the ThinkSpeak in the form of a graph. A doctor or guardian can log in to the web portal to monitor the patient’s data at any point in time. In case of emergencies, like temperature spike or heartbeat spike, etc. an email and SMS alert sent to the doctor and guardian’s email and mobile respectively. And at any point in time either a doctor or guardian can log into a web portal with patient unique credentials and can track patient’s data which would help medical services to send appropriate help in case of emergencies.

Conclusions: The main objective of the project is to incorporate the advantages of modern technology into the everlasting medical field. This project can also be customized to enhance the features. This basic model comprises a pulse sensor and temperature sensor. It can be customized as complex model with more features. The uniqueness of the project is the reports will be sent to the hospital management and patient caretaker frequently

Key words: LM35 Temperature Sensor, Pulse Rate Sensor, Arduino, ESP8266 Wi-Fi Module

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